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SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION

In this deliverable we present tests with glycerol and pyrolysis oil in a continuous Chemical Looping Plant, equipped to work with liquid fuels. Bio-oil is the main product of fast pyrolysis of biomass, and it has a higher volumetric energy density than the raw biomass. Glycerol is the waste product of biodiesel supply chain. Biodiesel production around the world has experienced a huge increase during last years. The annual global production reached 35 millions of tons in 2020 [1]. As by-product of biodiesel production, the glycerol has currently an oversupply, being estimated a total production of 3 millions of tons per annum [1]. Depending on the process used in biodiesel production, glycerol contents ranging from 40 to 85% can be found in the crude material. After adding mineral acid for purification, glycerol content increases to 80–85%, being water, methanol and dissolved salts the main impurities [2]. This byproduct does not require huge inputs for its production such as land and water.

The combustion and pyrolysis of these liquid fuels have been studied and modelled in MSCA projects in the past [3, 4]. So, it could be highly interesting to test these biofuels in a chemical looping combustion (CLC) unit. The great advantage of this process is that a concentrated CO₂ stream may be achieved with low energetic and economic costs. Thus,

this is a negative emissions technology (NET) if the bio-energy with CO₂ capture and storage (BECCS) concept is implemented.

SECTION 2: MATERIALS

A Ni-based material patented by CSIC [5] has been used as oxygen carrier for several chemical looping reforming (CLR) process with the purpose of obtaining syngas. Thus, CLR tests were performed previously using CH₄ [6], bioethanol [7] and diesel [8] as fuels.

In this project, the Ni18aAl oxygen carrier material was selected to be used in CLC tests with the objective of achieving the complete combustion of the fuel. The oxygen carrier was prepared by hot incipient wetness impregnation method [9] using α -Al₂O₃ as support, with a 18wt% of NiO as active phase. Table 1 shows the main properties of the oxygen carrier and the inert support used.

Table 1. Main properties of the oxygen carrier used and the inert support

Sample	α -Al ₂ O ₃	NiO18- α Al ₂ O ₃
Particle size (mm)	0.1–0.3	0.1–0.3
Apparent density (kg/m ³)	2000	2500
Porosity (%)	47.3	42.5
Specific surface area BET (m ² /g)	14.6	7.0
Mechanical strength (N)	–	4.1
XRD phases	α -Al ₂ O ₃	α -Al ₂ O ₃ , NiO, NiAl ₂ O ₄

Glycerol ($C_3H_8O_3$) with a purity of 95.9 vol% was used as fuel. For the correct feeding of the fuel it was necessary to mix glycerol with distilled water. A H_2O /glycerol molar ratio of 0.25 was used. Also, wood bio-oil with a purity of 68.5 wt% was used. The empirical formula free of water is C_3H_3O , which corresponds to an empirical molecular weight of 55 g/mol. The bio-oil used had one intrinsic H_2O /bio-oil molar ratio of 1.4.

SECTION 3: 1 kW_{th} CLC UNIT

A 1 kW_{th} Chemical Looping Combustion unit was used for glycerol and bio-oil combustion in the present work, see Fig. 1. The continuous unit is composed of two interconnected fluidized bed reactors (fuel and air reactors), a loop-seal, a riser, a system for gas and liquid feeding and a system for gas analysis. A complete description of the unit can be found elsewhere [7, 8]. In this work, a liquid injector was used to feed glycerol or bio-oil in the fuel reactor, which was located 2 cm above the distributor plate. The injector is composed by three concentric pipes. The fuel is fed in by the inner pipe (o.d. 1/8"). A N_2 flow is injected by a second concentric pipe to increase the velocity in the injection point and therefore to avoid solids return to the pipe. The last pipe is used for water cooling to avoid fuel evaporation before the injection point.

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The composition of the gas streams from the fuel and air reactors were determined by several on-line analyzers. In the fuel reactor CH₄, CO, and CO₂ were measured with a non-dispersive infrared analyzer (Siemens/Ultramat 23), and H₂ concentration was determined by using a thermal conductivity analyzer (Maihak S710). In the air reactor, O₂ was measured by a paramagnetic analyzer (Siemens/ Oxymat 5E), and CO₂ by a non-dispersive infrared analyzer (Siemens/Ultramat 23). This latter was used to determine the possible carbon deposition in the fuel reactor that, after being transported to the air reactor, is there burnt.

Fig. 1. 1 kW_{th} CLC continuous unit.

The oxygen carrier inventory in the system was ≈ 2 kg, being ≈ 0.8 kg inside the fuel reactor. The air flow in the air reactor was 1100 NL/h. In the fuel reactor, the total gas inlet flow was 150 NI/h. The glycerol and bio-oil feed flow was 135 and 180 g/h, which means a power input of ca. 650 W_{th} .

In Chemical Looping Combustion the control of the oxygen transferred to the fuel is carried out by controlling the oxygen carrier circulation rate in the unit. The stoichiometric oxygen required for the complete combustion of glycerol and bio-oil to CO_2 and H_2O is 7 and 6.5 mol of NiO per mol of fuel, respectively.

SECTION 4: PROCESS EVALUATION

The process performance is evaluated by using the combustion efficiency and the CO_2 capture rate. The combustion efficiency is related to the reactions involving the fuel conversion and the oxygen transference from the oxygen carrier to the fuel. Thus, complete combustion produces CO_2 and H_2O , while CO and H_2 may be produced by a partial oxidation of the fuel. In addition, the fuel may be reformed or decomposed to produce H_2 and CO, or even solid carbon which could be deposited on the oxygen carrier particles, gasified by H_2O or CO_2 and oxidized by NiO. Produced H_2 and CO may also be oxidized by the oxygen carrier. Also, the gas

composition may be balanced by the water gas shift reaction or CH_4 could be formed by methanation or as a secondary product of fuel decomposition. A general set of reactions for the conversion of glycerin ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$) or bio-oil ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{O}$) is reported as follows:

Fuel Reactor (FR)

Combustion

Partial Oxidation

Decomposition/Reforming

Carbon Gasification/Oxidation

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Combustion of Secondary Products

Water-Gas Shift Reaction

The combustion efficiency, η_{comb} , is calculated considering the unconverted products from the fuel reactor, mainly H_2 and CO , but also CH_4 and accumulated solid carbon on the particles were considered:

$$\eta_{comb} = \frac{sF_f - F_{CO} - F_{H_2} - 4F_{CH_4} - 2F_C}{sF_f}$$

where s is the stoichiometric factor for the complete combustion of the fuel to CO_2 and H_2O , and F_f , F_{CO} , F_{H_2} , F_{CH_4} and F_C are the molar flow of fuel, CO , H_2 , CH_4 and accumulated solid carbon on the particles, respectively.

Unconverted solid carbon may be transferred to the air reactor attached to the oxygen carrier particles. In this case, some carbon is burnt by air, and some CO_2 will be found in the exhaust gas stream from the air reactor, which will decrease the CO_2 capture rate (η_{CC}) being calculated as:

$$\eta_{CC} = \frac{cF_f - F_{CO_2,AR}}{cF_f}$$

where c is the number of carbon molecules in the fuel and $F_{CO_2,AR}$ is the molar CO_2 flow from the air reactor.

SECTION 5: RESULTS

The combustion tests with glycerin went smooth. Several tests were performed by changing the reactor temperature (750, 800 and 850 °C) and the oxygen carrier circulation rate in order to change the ratio of oxygen in NiO to fuel, $O_{NiO}/fuel$.

Figure 2 shows the gas composition for the different tests with glycerin. The H_2 and CO fractions were decreased as the oxygen to fuel ratio increased. Complete conversion of H_2 and CO to H_2O and CO_2 was not achieved due to the equilibrium condition for the reduction of NiO to Ni. Some CH_4 was also observed which decreased with temperature but it was barely affected by the oxygen to fuel ratio.

Figure 2: Gas composition during CLC tests with glycerin as a function of the $O_{NiO}/Fuel$ ratio and reacting temperature.

As selectivity to CO_2 varied with the operating conditions, different combustion efficiencies were achieved with different oxygen to fuel ratios ($O_{NiO}/Fuel$) and reacting temperatures. Thus, it was required a value of $O_{NiO}/Fuel = 9.5$ to maximize the combustion efficiency. This means that

there must be an excess of oxygen with respect to the stoichiometric ($O_{NiO}/Fuel = 7$) of 35 %. To consider the variation of the combustion efficiency with the excess of oxygen, Figure 3 shows its variation as a function of the oxygen carrier to fuel ratio, ϕ , defined by:

$$\phi = \frac{[O_{NiO}/Fuel]_{current}}{[O_{NiO}/Fuel]_{stoichiometric}}$$

Figure 3: Combustion efficiency during CLC tests with glycerin as a function of the oxygen carrier to fuel ratio (ϕ) and reacting temperature.

In addition, no CO_2 was detected in the exhaust gas stream from the air reactor when glycerin was used as fuel. Therefore, the CO_2 capture rate was 100 % in all cases.

The operation with bio-oil was more complex than with glycerin. Under some conditions, the fuel injection system was blocked by carbon deposition. In addition, bio-oil showed a greater trend towards the carbon formation on the oxygen carrier particles. Thus, experimental conditions were limited to 750 and 850 °C, and $O_{NiO}/Fuel$ ratios of 6.5, 8 and 9.5. Considering the stoichiometric $O_{NiO}/Fuel$ ratio for bio-oil is 6.5, the oxygen carrier to fuel ratio, ϕ , was 1.0, 1.2 and 1.5, respectively.

Figure 4(a) shows the fraction of carbon in bio-oil being deposited on the oxygen carrier particles in the fuel reactor. About 20% of carbon was

deposited at 850 °C, and it was not affected by the oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio. In addition, only a small fraction of the deposited carbon was burned in the air reactor. Therefore, the deposited carbon was accumulated on the oxygen carrier particles with the operation time, and the CO₂ capture rate was close to 100% because the presence of CO₂ in the exhaust gas stream from the air reactor was of low relevance; see Figure 4(b). The carbon fraction deposited on the oxygen carrier decreased at 750 °C and it was more reactive than at 850 °C. Thus, about one half of deposited carbon was burned in the air reactor, decreasing the CO₂ capture rate; see Figures 4(a) and 4(b). However, the carbon deposition decreased with the oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio, and it was undetectable at $\phi=1.5$. Therefore, bio-oil was completely converted to gaseous products in the fuel reactor at 750 °C and $\phi=1.5$.

Figure 4: Effect of the oxygen carrier-to-fuel ratio (ϕ) and the reacting temperature on (a) the carbon fraction being deposited (closed symbols) or accumulated (open symbols) on the oxygen carrier particles; and (b) the CO₂ capture rate.

The gas composition in the fuel reactor is shown in Figure 5. Unconverted products decreased with the O_{NiO}/Fuel ratio. At 750 °C, the CO/H₂ ratio was about 1, but it increased higher than the unity at 850 °C. In addition, some CH₄ was detected, which also decreased with the O_{NiO}/Fuel ratio. However, most of unconverted product was solid carbon, especially at 850 °C. Thus, the combustion efficiency at 750 °C was higher than at 850 °C. The combustion efficiency at 750 °C and $\phi = 1.5$ was close to the

maximum allowed by the equilibrium thermodynamic for the NiO reduction to Ni.

Figure 5: Gas composition during CLC tests with bio-oil as a function of the $O_{NiO}/Fuel$ ratio and reacting temperature.

Figure 6: Combustion efficiency during CLC tests with bio-oil as a function of the oxygen carrier to fuel ratio (ϕ) and reacting temperature.

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